

SPYDER: QoS-aware Radio Resource Allocation in Multiuser ISAC-capable C-V2X Networks

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ABSTRACT Integrated Sensing and Communication (ISAC) in cellular vehicle-to-everything (C-V2X) systems presents a promising solution for enhancing road safety and traffic efficiency. However, it also poses significant challenges in radio resource management, particularly in efficiently allocating time-frequency (TF) resources to meet distinct Quality of Service (QoS) requirements, minimizing resource occupancy for high-resolution radar sensing, and mitigating coordination overhead and interference in a multiuser ISAC-capable C-V2X network. To overcome these challenges, we propose a novel uncoordinated QoS-aware radio resource allocation (RRA) scheme for a multiuser ISAC-capable C-V2X sidelink system. Unlike existing approaches, the proposed scheme eliminates the need for inter-vehicle coordination, ensuring low spectral requirements while maintaining robust sensing and communication performance in dense, high-mobility environments. Specifically, we extend semi-persistent scheduling (SPS) to enable joint data transmission and radar sensing, dynamically selecting TF resources based on ISAC QoS demands. A key innovation of our approach is the introduction of a sparse random pattern yielding dynamic interleaving (SPYDER) based OFDM grid, which employs non-uniform interleaving of OFDM symbols and subcarriers to support high-resolution radar sensing while reducing resource overhead for communication operations. Since SPYDER adopts a non-uniform TF interleaved OFDM grid, it may experience multiuser resource overlapping that could degrade radar detection performance. To counteract this, we employ sparse reconstruction algorithms within the compressed sensing framework, enhancing flexibility in TF resource allocation and providing high-resolution radar sensing despite uncoordinated resource selection. We evaluate the proposed scheme's performance through numerical simulations and compare it against state-of-the-art methods. The findings highlight the SPYDER grid's efficiency, robustness to interference, and minimal resource occupancy, making it suitable for next-generation C-V2X networks.

INDEX TERMS Integrated Sensing and Communication (ISAC), C-V2X sidelink, time-frequency (TF) resource allocation, compressed sensing.

I. Introduction

THE evolution of wireless communication technologies in intelligent transportation system (ITS) has driven the emergence of vehicle-to-everything (V2X) communication. This technology facilitates seamless information sharing between vehicles (vehicle-to-vehicle (V2V)), pedestrians (vehicle-to-pedestrian (V2P)), infrastructure (vehicle-to-infrastructure (V2I)), and roadside units, contributing to

safer, more efficient, and comfortable transportation systems through well-defined vehicular communication standards [1]. Two key wireless technologies that support V2X communication are Dedicated Short Range Communication (DSRC) (commonly referred to as ITS-G5) and cellular-V2X (C-V2X). While DSRC employs WiFi-based protocols such as IEEE 802.11p and 802.11bd, C-V2X is built on cellular standards, including LTE-V2X and NR-V2X. DSRC,

being one of the pioneering V2X technologies, faces significant limitations in dense, high-mobility scenarios, including restricted coverage, low data rates, lack of guaranteed Quality of Service (QoS), and unpredictable channel access delays [2]. On the other hand, building on standard cellular technologies, the Third Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) has developed a cellular-based vehicular communication standard known as C-V2X. C-V2X offers several advantages over DSRC, such as a longer communication range and better reliability in dense vehicular environments. In Release 14 and 15, 3GPP proposed two C-V2X air interfaces to support advanced features: Uu interface for infrastructure-assisted communication, and PC5 interface (also known as sidelink) for direct communication [3]. The sidelink mode is responsible for direct V2V communication without support from the infrastructure or base station (BS). Despite these advantages, C-V2X still faces challenges in highly dynamic vehicular environments, including resource contention, coordination overhead, and mutual interference in dense network scenarios [4].

As autonomous driving technology progresses towards Level 5 autonomy, advanced ITS applications such as intelligent platooning, cooperative lane merging, and advanced accident prevention demand stringent performance requirements for reliability, low latency, and high-resolution environmental sensing [5]. These critical requirements surpass the capabilities of existing V2X technologies. The emerging fifth generation-Advanced (5G-A) and sixth-generation (6G) networks are envisioned to address these challenges through Integrated Sensing and Communications (ISAC) technology [6]. The core concept of ISAC lies in the shared utilization of wireless resources such as time, frequency, beam, and power for both sensing and communication, using a unified hardware platform, thereby meeting the stringent demands of future ITS applications. By integrating ISAC into C-V2X, the vehicles can not only exchange data but also sense their surroundings to detect obstacles, estimate distances, measure relative velocities, and monitor road conditions [7]. This integration significantly enhances spectrum efficiency, reduces latency, and lowers hardware costs, while enabling advanced vehicular applications. Despite its potential, ISAC integration into C-V2X presents several challenges. The highly dynamic vehicular environment, characterized by high mobility, varying vehicle densities, and complex propagation conditions, creates difficulties in balancing the dual requirements of sensing and communication. High-resolution radar sensing, crucial for accurate environmental perception, imposes significant radio resource overheads, potentially degrading communication performance. Moreover, avoiding time-frequency (TF) resource collisions to mitigate interference among multiple vehicles performing joint communication and sensing in diverse traffic scenarios is a complex task. Additionally, signaling and coordination overhead in high mobility dense vehicular networks, in terms of frequent channel sensing for available TF resource selection, pose

significant challenges to achieving ultra-low latency requirements of C-V2X. Overcoming these challenges is crucial to realizing the full potential of ISAC in C-V2X. It demands QoS-aware radio resource allocation (RRA) schemes that enable flexible and efficient sharing of TF resources within a multiuser ISAC-capable C-V2X network.

A. Related Work

Extensive research efforts have been dedicated to ISAC waveform design and resource allocation to improve communication and radar sensing performance. The work in [8] pioneered the concept of designing orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM) waveform for simultaneous communication and radar sensing. Similarly, the works in [9], [10] explore the integration of radar sensing capabilities into mobile communication networks, leveraging existing infrastructure and advanced features of fifth generation (5G) to enable ISAC in 5G-V2X. To integrate radar sensing into C-V2X systems, mainly three types of TF resource allocation mechanisms have been studied: sensing with standard reference signals (RS) [11]–[15], sensing with data payload signals [16], [17], and sensing with optimized TF resource patterns [18]–[21]. In the case of sensing with RS, the authors in [11] employed channel state information reference signals (CSI-RS) and demodulation reference signals (DMRS) for sensing, and analyzed the impact of TF resource mapping on sensing performance. A radar sensing approach utilizing positioning reference signals (PRS) is introduced in [12], where the accuracy of distance and velocity estimation is thoroughly evaluated. In [14], algorithms for angle and delay estimation are developed using sounding reference signals (SRS). The study highlights the advantages of SRS compared to other standard signals for localization in V2X networks. In [15], the authors introduced an ISAC approach that leverages the synchronization signal block (SSB) and incorporates system information block 1 (SIB1) to support 5G-A and 6G systems. Among these different RS signals, DMRS signals are user-specific, always transmitted alongside the data payload, and exhibit randomness and irregularity over time, necessitating sensing algorithms capable of handling such variability. In case of sensing with data payload, the work [16] utilized full OFDM data payload signal to provide high-resolution range and velocity estimations via 2D multiple signal classification (MUSIC) algorithm. In [17] both data payload and DMRS are used for radar signal processing, and the OFDM waveform is further optimized by minimizing the Cramer Rao Bound (CRB) on delay and Doppler estimation. With the optimized TF resource patterns, the authors in [18] proposed an optimized OFDM-based ISAC waveform with minimization of CRB for delay and Doppler estimation while addressing resource occupancy and under-sampling issues through matrix completion via Schatten p-norm approximation. While this work demonstrates that placing resources at the edges of the OFDM grid can improve radar resolution, these methods

assume coordinated resource allocation. In [19], the authors presented two radar processing techniques that utilize pilot signals—one using continuous pilots and the other using stepped pilots—to improve sensing performance in joint vehicular communication and radar systems. Similarly, the authors in [20] introduced a stepped carrier OFDM waveform with linear and non-linear hopping patterns to achieve high range and velocity resolution, and to maximize the signal-to-radar (SIR) interference ratio. However, using an equidistant or uniform interleaving OFDM grid leads to a reduction in the maximum unambiguous distance and velocity. To address this issue, the authors in [21] proposed the use of non-equidistant subcarrier interleaving to achieve a full, unambiguous measurable distance range. Additionally, this work introduced a compressed sensing (CS) method based on the orthogonal matching pursuit (OMP) algorithm to deal with the increased range sidelobes caused by non-equidistant subcarrier interleaving in the OFDM grid.

While these above-mentioned works have demonstrated the feasibility of ISAC in vehicular networks, they have several limitations. Most of the work focuses on centralized scheduling where TF resource allocation is performed by the BS (i.e., coordinated allocation). Some studies explore ISAC in the millimeter wave (mmWave) spectrum but do not focus on standardized C-V2X sidelink wireless access technologies at sub-6 GHz. Only [22], [23] focus on sidelink resource allocation at sub-6 GHz, where the authors assessed how sidelink’s mode 2 resource allocation affects radar sensing performance by using the same TF resources for both sidelink communication and radar sensing. However, allocating the same resources for both tasks is not efficient due to the distinct performance requirements of radar and communication, particularly in complex dynamic C-V2X environments. Additionally, they consider monostatic radar sensing that requires full-duplex transceivers in vehicles, which is incompatible with 3GPP-based sidelink communication. On another note, while existing radar sensing algorithms for sparse OFDM signals have made significant progress, they still exhibit several major limitations. Some algorithms experience high Doppler sidelobes because their OFDM grid does not account for sparsity in the time domain. Others do not resolve the grid mismatch problem, and those that do offer solutions to grid mismatch often have high computational complexity, which restricts their practical application in real-time scenarios.

B. Contributions

Building on the gaps identified in the literature and addressing the challenges of TF resource allocation and the unstructured sparsity of the OFDM grid in multiuser ISAC-capable C-V2X networks, this paper makes the following key contributions:

- This work introduces a novel QoS-aware RRA framework for a multiuser ISAC-capable sidelink system at sub-6 GHz, optimizing the allocation of TF resources

based on sensing and communication key performance indicators (KPIs). Unlike traditional approaches, the proposed scheme removes the need for inter-vehicle coordination, making it well-suited for decentralized vehicular networks. It minimizes TF resource occupancy, ensuring efficient radar sensing and communication in dense, high-mobility environments. Inspired by our previous work [24], the proposed RRA scheme adopts the semi-persistent scheduling (SPS) based resource selection mechanism for joint data packet transmission and low-resolution sensing. However, to achieve high-resolution sensing in dense vehicular environments, unlike full grid [24] or edge allocation [18], which requires cooperative or centralized coordination, the proposed RRA scheme employs a non-uniform, dynamically interleaved sparse OFDM grid called sparse random pattern yielding dynamic interleaving (SPYDER) that significantly reduces resource collision in multiuser, uncoordinated ISAC networks. SPYDER autonomously selects TF resources, making it ideal for non-cooperative vehicular ISAC scenarios while minimizing radar resource overhead.

- Due to the non-uniform SPYDER grid structure, conventional periodogram-based processing introduces ambiguities in range-Doppler maps. To overcome this, we propose a low-complexity CS based signal processing framework, which enables high-resolution target detection without imposing structural constraints on the OFDM grid. Additionally, the performance of the CS algorithm is compared with conventional radar signal processing methods.
- A detailed performance analysis of key communication metrics such as packet reception ratio (PRR), packet inter-reception delay (PID), and channel busy ratio (CBR) is provided alongside radar sensing metrics including range-Doppler resolution, peak-to-sidelobe-level ratio (PSLR), and root-mean-squared-error (RMSE) in range and velocity estimation. These evaluations are performed under varying vehicular densities and resource configurations to highlight the trade-offs between communication and sensing in multiuser ISAC-capable C-V2X sidelink.

This work builds upon our previous work [24], where a full-grid resource allocation strategy was employed for high-resolution radar sensing in ISAC-capable C-V2X sidelink system. However, that work was limited to a single-node sensing scenario and did not consider resource collisions or multiuser interference. In contrast, this paper introduces a novel SPYDER-based resource allocation scheme to enable high-resolution radar sensing in dense vehicular environments without inter-vehicle coordination. Additionally, unlike [24], this paper assumes bistatic ISAC system in compliance with half-duplex C-V2X sidelink communication, and analyzes the synchronization errors due to different locations of the transmitting and receiving vehicles in the scenario.

FIGURE 1. Illustration of a multiuser ISAC-capable sidelink scenario, where multiple vehicles on the highway communicate with one another and sense the neighboring vehicles (acting as passive targets) in the presence of roadside scatterers (acting as clutter).

Furthermore, a CS based signal processing framework is introduced to address ambiguities in range-Doppler maps caused by SPYDER resource selection.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section II describes the multiuser ISAC-capable sidelink system model, along with the TF resource grid structure, signal model and synchronization errors. In section III, the proposed RRA framework is presented. Section IV describes the radar sensing parameter estimation using the CS based signal processing framework. Section V presents the simulation setup and extensive numerical evaluations of the radar and communication performance metrics. Finally, Section VI concludes the paper.

II. Multiuser ISAC-capable Sidelink System

A. System Model

We consider a multiuser ISAC-capable sidelink system deployed on a two-way highway with three lanes in each direction as shown in Figure 1. The vehicles, equipped with ISAC-capable transceivers, are engaged in two main functionalities: sidelink communication and radar sensing. The vehicles exchange data with one another through sidelink signals while also leveraging the reflected sidelink signals to sense their surrounding environment. The system operates in compliance with the half-duplex mode of sidelink communication. A transmitting vehicle (Tx) sends data packets to a receiving vehicle (Rx) over the sidelink channel. At the Rx, three types of signals are received: 1) The direct signal (line-of-sight (LOS)) from the Tx for sidelink communication, 2) the reflected sidelink signals (non-line-of-sight (NLOS)) from surrounding vehicles acting as passive radar targets, and 3) the scattered sidelink signals (NLOS) from the roadside scatterers, acting as clutter. By processing these reflected signals, the Rx not only decodes the communication data but also functions as a bistatic radar to estimate the key

radar parameters such as the range and relative velocity of nearby vehicles. This dual-purpose operation integrates radar sensing and sidelink communication, creating a multiuser ISAC-capable sidelink system. In this paper, GPS-disciplined oscillators are assumed to be utilized across the Tx and Rx vehicles to ensure synchronization among them, eliminating any timing or carrier-frequency offsets. However, we acknowledge the importance of synchronization in bistatic ISAC where residual synchronization errors can degrade both communication and radar sensing performance. We discuss synchronization issues in Section II-D, where we analyze the impact of residual timing and frequency offsets on system performance. Sidelink communication demands reliable packet delivery (PRR and PID), while radar sensing requires accurate range-velocity estimation (low RMSE and high PSLR).

B. Time-Frequency (TF) Resource Grid

The TF resource grid is based on a 5G-NR OFDM grid in which radio resources are structured in the time and frequency domain, with the smallest unit being a resource element (RE), defined as a single subcarrier over one OFDM symbol as shown in Figure 2. Time domain resources are:

- **Frames:** with a fixed duration of 10 ms.
- **Subframes:** each frame is divided into 10 subframes, each lasting 1 ms.
- **Slots:** a subframe contains one or more slots, depending on the chosen numerology. With the standard cyclic prefix (CP), each slot consists of 14 OFDM symbols.

Frequency domain resources are organized into:

- **Physical Resource Blocks (PRBs):** each PRB consists of 12 consecutive subcarriers with subcarrier spacing (SCS) denoted by Δf . The bandwidth of a PRB varies

FIGURE 2. Time-Frequency (TF) resource grid structure.

with Δf . For example, with $\Delta f = 30$ kHz, a PRB occupies 360 kHz. Higher SCS values result in narrower PRB durations in time.

- **Subchannels:** a subchannel comprises K consecutive PRBs, where K can be selected from predefined values (10, 12, 15, 20, 25, 50, 75, 100). The number of subchannels N_{sub} is determined based on the bandwidth configuration and PRB grouping.

This TF resource grid structure provides flexibility in allocating resources for both communication and radar sensing in the multiuser ISAC-capable sidelink system with diverse QoS requirements.

1) Communication Resource Structure

For sidelink communication, a data packet occupies a fixed and contiguous TF region in the OFDM resource grid as represented in yellow color in Figure 2. Each transmission occupies a slot in the time domain, and a certain number of PRBs or subchannels in the frequency domain. The exact number of PRBs required depends on the Modulation and Coding Scheme (MCS) chosen for the transmission. The lower the MCS, the higher the number of PRBs required to accommodate the data packet, and vice versa. Consequently, a sidelink data packet transmission spans 14 OFDM symbols in the time domain and $12 \times K \times N_{sub}$ subcarriers in the frequency domain.

2) Radar Resource Structure - SPYDER Grid

To achieve high-resolution radar sensing, a sparse TF interleaving strategy is employed for radar resource allocation across the OFDM grid. As shown in Figure 3, four sparse TF resource configurations — uniform grid, non-uniform grid, edge grid and the proposed SPYDER grid — are analyzed. Their range-Doppler (RD) maps are shown in Figure 4. Uniform grid is shown in Figure 3a, where

resources are evenly spaced along both subcarriers and OFDM symbols. Such grids introduce equipower aliasing peaks in the RD map (Figure 4a), making it challenging to distinguish true targets from aliased ones and reducing the maximum unambiguous range and velocity. The non-

FIGURE 3. Radar resource grids: (a) uniform grid, (b) non-uniform grid, (c) edge grid, and (d) SPYDER grid.

uniform grid, shown in Figure 3b, addresses some of these limitations by introducing unequal spacing along subcarriers and OFDM symbols while maintaining consistent subcarriers interleaving across OFDM symbols. This reduces the power of aliasing peaks in the RD map (Figure 4b), making it easier to identify the true target. However, the residual aliasing peaks, also known as random spurs along the range and Doppler axis, can still mask weaker targets, reducing the radar's detection capability. The edge grid is shown in Figure 3c in which resources are allocated at the edges of the grid to maximize effective bandwidth and time duration, achieving high-resolution sensing. While range resolution is improved, sidelobes along the Doppler axis persist in the RD map (Figure 4c), which can obscure weaker targets. This configuration assumes centralized or cooperative resource allocation, making it impractical in decentralized multiuser vehicular networks. Finally, the SPYDER grid is shown in Figure 3d in which resources are interleaved with non-uniform and dynamic spacing along both subcarriers and OFDM symbols. The subcarriers interleaving changes dynamically along OFDM symbols, resulting in a randomized and broader spectral coverage. With the SPYDER grid, the range independent spurs/sidelobes are reduced in the RD map improving the range detection of weaker targets as shown in Figure 4d. However, the Doppler spurs/sidelobes remain similar to those in the non-uniform grid. To overcome the Doppler processing with the SPYDER grid, a CS

algorithm [25] is employed. The SPYDER grid drastically reduces the spectral and temporal resources needed for high-resolution radar sensing, freeing up more resources for V2V communication. Moreover, the autonomous selection of the SPYDER grid eliminates the need for strict inter-vehicle coordination and reduces the chances of resource collision in dense vehicular scenarios.

FIGURE 4. Range-Doppler (RD) maps: (a) RD map of uniform grid, (b) RD map of non-uniform grid, (c) RD map of edge grid, and (d) RD map of SPYDER grid

However, in practical scenarios involving non-cooperating multiple users, it is nearly impossible to perfectly allocate non-overlapping TF resources as an interference mitigation measure. Some degree of interference is inevitable, especially in dense environments. For example, as shown in Figure 5, a transmitting vehicle Tx-1, selects communication and radar resources (yellow colored resources) from a resource pool shared by another vehicle Tx-2. As a result, both vehicles may compete for the same TF resources, leading to resource collisions as represented in red color resources. This resource overlapping is the source of mutual interference which elevates the noise levels in the range-Doppler map of the radar receiver obscuring weaker targets and degrading detection and estimation performance. To mitigate this interference caused by resource overlapping a two-step procedure—interference detection and cancellation—is employed. Interference detection leverages the distinct amplitude characteristics of interference (often several dB stronger than target reflections) to identify corrupted resource elements using an adaptive thresholding mechanism like CFAR [26]. Subsequently, interference cancellation employs a straightforward *zeroing* method in which interfered resources are removed from the grid before further processing, enabling

robust target detection in the multiuser ISAC network. An alternative approach to mitigating interference in multiuser ISAC systems is the assignment of orthogonal or pseudo-random sensing waveforms, ensuring that even in the presence of resource collisions, mutual interference is minimized. However, such an approach requires explicit coordination among vehicles to enforce orthogonality, which contradicts the fundamental motivation behind SPYDER—enabling uncoordinated, autonomous resource selection with minimal overhead. Nevertheless, future research may explore a hybrid approach that integrates orthogonal or pseudo-random waveforms with SPYDER’s dynamic TF allocation to further enhance interference resilience while maintaining the scheme’s low-overhead advantages in dense vehicular networks.

FIGURE 5. SPYDER grid selection by two vehicles: Tx-1 (yellow) and Tx-2 (green) with some resource collisions (red) in a multiuser ISAC-capable sidelink network.

C. Signal Model

The transmitted signal $x : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ in the complex baseband comprises N_b subcarriers and M_b OFDM symbols, forming an $N_b \times M_b$ transmission resource grid \mathbf{X} . Within \mathbf{X} , the transmitting vehicle selects two subsets Ω_c and Ω_s of resources from the resource set Ω for joint communication and radar sensing, respectively. The subset $\Omega_c \subset \Omega$ consists of contiguous TF resources, $\Omega_s \subset \Omega$ consists of random non-contiguous TF resources, and Ω is defined as $\Omega \triangleq \{(n, m) \mid 0 < n \leq N_b, 0 < m \leq M_b\}$. Hence, the transmit signal x is given by

$$x(t) = \sum_{m=0}^{M_b-1} \left(\sum_{n=0}^{N_b-1} \mathbf{X}_{n,m} e^{j\frac{2\pi}{T}nt} \right) \text{rect}_T(t - mT_o), \quad (1)$$

such that

$$\mathbf{X}_{n,m} \in \begin{cases} \mathcal{A}_{n,m}, & \text{if } \{n, m\} \in \Omega_c \cup \Omega_s \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where $\mathcal{A}_{n,m}$, T , and T_o represent the modulation symbol, the rectangular pulse duration, and the OFDM symbol duration (including the CP), respectively. After removing the CP and

applying the Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT), the received OFDM grid at the receiving vehicle can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{Y}_{n,m} = & \gamma_{los} \mathbf{X}_{n,m} e^{-j2\pi n \Delta f \tau_{los}} e^{j2\pi m T_o \alpha_{los}} \\ & + \sum_{\ell=1}^L \gamma_{\ell} \mathbf{X}_{n,m} e^{-j2\pi n \Delta f \tau_{\ell}} e^{j2\pi m T_o \alpha_{\ell}} \\ & + \sum_{q=1}^Q \gamma_q \mathbf{X}_{n,m} e^{-j2\pi n \Delta f \tau_q} e^{j2\pi m T_o \alpha_q} \\ & + \mathbf{I}_{n,m} + \mathbf{Z}_{n,m}, \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

The first component represents the LOS signal where γ_{los} , τ_{los} , and α_{los} represent the complex amplitude, propagation delay, and Doppler shift of the Tx vehicle, respectively. The second component corresponds to reflections from L target vehicles with γ_{ℓ} , τ_{ℓ} and α_{ℓ} represent the complex attenuation coefficient, bi-static delay and Doppler shift of the ℓ -th target vehicle, respectively. The third component accounts for reflections from Q roadside scatterers, with γ_q , τ_q , and α_q being the corresponding parameters for the q -th scatterer, and $\mathbf{I}_{n,m}$ is the interference from other vehicles transmitting at n -th subcarrier and m -th OFDM symbol (i.e., overlapping TF resources). Finally, the noise is modeled as $\mathbf{Z}_{n,m} \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, N_0)$ representing the AWGN at the n -th subcarrier and m -th OFDM symbol.

D. Synchronization Errors

In the previous subsection, the signal model is formulated under the assumption of perfect synchronization between Tx and Rx vehicles. However, in practical bistatic ISAC systems, ensuring time and frequency synchronization is challenging due to the independent oscillator clocks at the transmitter and receiver, leading to time offset (TO) and carrier frequency offset (CFO). TO arises due to the lack of a synchronized time reference between the transmitter and receiver, as each relies on its own local oscillator (LO) to generate timing signals for transmission and reception. Since these clock sources operate independently, the Rx perceived time may differ from the actual transmission time, leading to an unknown time shift or offset. On the other hand, CFO primarily arises due to difference between the LOs of the transmitter and receiver. Since no two oscillators can produce identical frequencies, the carrier frequencies generated by independent LOs will inherently differ, resulting in CFO and random phase offsets. Considering these offsets, we extend the received signal model given in (3) as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{Y}_{n,m} = & \gamma_{los} \mathbf{X}_{n,m} e^{-j2\pi n \Delta f (\tau_{los} + \delta_{\tau})} e^{j2\pi m T_o (\alpha_{los} + \delta_{\alpha})} \\ & + \sum_{\ell=1}^L \gamma_{\ell} \mathbf{X}_{n,m} e^{-j2\pi n \Delta f (\tau_{\ell} + \delta_{\tau})} e^{j2\pi m T_o (\alpha_{\ell} + \delta_{\alpha})} \\ & + \sum_{q=1}^Q \gamma_q \mathbf{X}_{n,m} e^{-j2\pi n \Delta f (\tau_q + \delta_{\tau})} e^{j2\pi m T_o (\alpha_q + \delta_{\alpha})} \\ & + \mathbf{I}_{n,m} + \mathbf{Z}_{n,m}, \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where, δ_{τ} and δ_{α} represent TO and CFO respectively. These offsets are assumed to be the same for all the paths and remain unchanged within the sensing period. TO and CFO, if not estimated and compensated well, can significantly degrade both communication and radar sensing performance. In communication, TO and CFO make the constellation diagram noisy (broadened) and rotated (phase shift), resulting in increased symbol error rate. Whereas in radar sensing, these offsets introduce distortions in delay and Doppler shift estimation leading to inaccurate range and velocity estimation. Another type of offset caused by the differences in the sampling frequency between digital-to-analog converter (DAC) in the Tx and the analog-to-digital converter (ADC) in the Rx is known as sampling frequency offset (SFO). SFO combines the effects of TO and CFO introducing range-Doppler migration while deteriorating both range and Doppler shift resolutions [27]. For the sake of simplicity, we assume that the Tx and Rx have exactly the same sampling frequency resulting in the nonoccurrence of SFO.

Existing communication systems employ algorithms [28] to compensate for TO and CFO; however, these methods treat sensing parameters such as delay and Doppler shift as unwanted distortions and eliminate them [29]. This renders conventional techniques unsuitable for sensing applications, as delay and Doppler are essential channel parameters used to characterize the physical environment. To address this problem, several approaches are reported in the literature [30] such as Global Positioning System (GPS) based synchronization and single node based synchronization (e.g., cross-antenna cross-correlation (CACC) [31] and cross-antenna signal ratio (CASR) [32]). In this work, we adopt GPS disciplined clock (GPSDO) based synchronization due to its ability to provide a global and highly accurate time reference, which is essential for mitigating TO and CFO in ISAC systems. Unlike single-node-based synchronization, which relies on the presence of a LOS link and additional processing, GPSDO-based synchronization offers a practical and scalable solution. To ensure a realistic evaluation in our simulation framework, we consider the performance of a multi-band GNSS timing module, e.g., the u-blox M2-ZED-F9T, which achieves timing accuracy up to 5 ns, making it ideal for our ISAC-capable C-V2X network. While this work focuses on resource allocation for ISAC-capable vehicular networks, synchronization remains a key challenge in bistatic ISAC systems. Future research will explore advanced synchronization techniques tailored specifically for ISAC, including robust TO and CFO estimation methods that preserve sensing parameters such as delay and Doppler shift.

III. Proposed Approach

This section presents the proposed RRA framework, for a multiuser ISAC-capable C-V2X sidelink network, wherein each vehicle independently selects and manages its resources to perform joint communication and radar sensing. By eliminating inter-vehicle coordination, this RRA approach

is particularly suited for scenarios with limited or no BS coverage. The complete workflow of the proposed scheme is shown in Figure 6. The process begins with the ISAC QoS management at the transmitting vehicle, denoted as V_i , where the required KPIs for communication and radar sensing operations are analyzed.

- 1) **Communication QoS Management:** Ensures robust communication by maintaining KPIs such as PRR and PID.
- 2) **Radar Sensing QoS Management:** Focuses on KPIs like range-Doppler resolution, PSLR, and RMSE for radar parameter estimation.

These KPIs are exchanged among multiple vehicles involved in the sensing and communication tasks.

A. Communication and Low Resolution Sensing Resource Allocation (C&LRS-RA)

Based on the communication KPIs, V_i selects a subset Ω_c of contiguous TF resources (e.g., subchannels and slots) from the shared resource pool using the standard SPS scheme to perform joint communication and low resolution sensing (LRS). SPS is a well-established resource allocation scheme defined by the 3GPP for 5G-NR V2X sidelink communication, particularly for periodic traffic. The approach offers a balance between low overhead and efficient resource utilization, making it suitable for autonomous and decentralized vehicular networks. The main steps involved in the C&LRS-RA are briefly discussed below.

1) Resource Sensing

As shown in Figure 7, when V_i wants to select TF resources at time slot t_p for packet transmission, it first senses the resources used by other vehicles in the immediate past 1s window called sensing window defined in the interval $[t_p - T_{sense}, t_p - 1]$, where T_{sense} is the sensing window duration that can be set as 100ms (short-term sensing) for aperiodic transmissions or 1100ms (long-term sensing) for periodic transmissions. During T_{sense} , V_i measures the sidelink reference signal received power (SL-RSRP) across all the resources as the interference values.

2) Resource Exclusion

The sensing window measurements are used to exclude the resources in the selection window (SW). The SW is a list L_1 of all the candidate resources in the interval $[t_p + T_1, t_p + T_2]$, where T_1 and T_2 depend on the packet delay budget (PDB). Within the SW, V_i identifies the free resources and stores them in a second list L_2 after excluding the unavailable resources. The exclusion of resources from L_1 is done based on the following conditions.

- The decoded sidelink control information (SCI) declares that the resource is occupied.

- The SL-RSRP level of the resource is greater than the predefined threshold γ_{th} .

Moreover, due to half-duplex transmissions, V_i cannot monitor the slot of its past transmissions in its sensing window, all candidate resources reserved in that slot are also excluded. After the resource exclusion, V_i checks if the number of the available resources in L_2 is equal to or higher than $X\%$ of all the candidate resources in L_1 . If this is not the case then γ_{th} is increased by 3 dB, and the process is repeated until the available resources in L_2 become at least $X\%$. The set of values for $X\%$ in 5G-NR V2X is 20%, 35%, 50%, which is selected based on the configuration and service priority.

3) Resource Selection & Reservation

After resource exclusion, V_i selects a subset Ω_c of contiguous TF resources randomly from L_2 for packet transmission. The selected subchannel will be reserved for the next reselection counter (RC) number of transmissions with a specific resource reservation interval (RRI). The value of RC is chosen randomly from the range $[5, 15]$ for the $RRI \geq 100$ ms, and is decreased by one after each packet transmission. The neighboring vehicles are also informed of the reservation information via the SCI.

4) Resource Reselection

When RC reaches 0, V_i has two options: either it keeps the same subchannel for the next transmissions with probability p_{keep} or it selects a new subchannel with probability $(1 - p_{keep})$. The value of p_{keep} can be chosen between 0 and 0.8 depending on the configuration. Additionally, resource reselection is required in two other scenarios: when the new packet cannot fit into the previously reserved subchannel (e.g., due to a change in packet size), or when the current reservation fails to meet the PDB requirements of the new packet (e.g., the interval between packet generation and the next resource reservation exceeds the PDB limit).

B. High Resolution Sensing Resource Allocation (HRS-RA)

If high resolution sensing (HRS) is required, V_i selects additional TF resources beyond those selected for C&LRS, enabling more accurate range and velocity estimation. The steps involved in the HRS-RA are explained below.

1) Resource Calculation for HRS

The count of extra TF resources for HRS is derived from the HRS KPIs reported in the ISAC QoS report. The KPIs of HRS include range resolution Δr and velocity resolution Δv . Based on these KPIs, the sensing bandwidth B_s and sensing time T_s corresponding to the total required TF resources for HRS are calculated as follows.

$$B_s = \frac{c}{\Delta r}, \quad (5)$$

FIGURE 6. Workflow of the proposed ISAC-enabled SPS scheme: The left side of the workflow diagram illustrates the main steps involved in the C&LRS-RA, while the right side depicts the primary steps for enabling HRS.

$$T_s = \frac{c}{2f_c \Delta v}, \quad (6)$$

where $B_s = N_b \Delta f$ and $T_s = M_b T_o$.

2) SPYDER Resource Selection

With this information, V_i randomly selects SPYDER resources, a subset Ω_s of arbitrarily non-contiguous TF resources, without any coordination with other vehicles as shown in Figure 7. The SPYDER reduces the resource overhead of HRS on the communication transmissions by exploiting the sparsity within the $B_s \times T_s$ OFDM grid. The V_i then transmits the data packet along with the SPYDER sensing signals on the selected TF resources over the sidelink channel.

In high-density vehicular environments, SPYDER selection is prone to severe resource collisions. The zeroing

or elimination of very high number of collided resources may lead to an insufficient number of non-overlapping TF resources required for reliable radar parameter recovery via the CS framework. To address this issue, a resource reuse distance judgment mechanism is employed [33]. The mechanism operates as follows:

- Upon detecting collisions in the SPYDER, the collided resources are excluded and stored in a list L_3 in ascending order according to their interference levels. This results in a remaining U number of usable collision-free resources in the SPYDER.
- If $U < U_{min}$, where U_{min} is the minimum number of TF resources required for reliable sparse recovery, further steps are initiated. Here U_{min} is derived as follows

$$U_{min} \geq Ck \log\left(\frac{N_b M_b}{k}\right), \quad (7)$$

FIGURE 7. Illustration of the C&LRS resource selection using the standard SPS procedure followed by uncoordinated SPYDER resource selection to realize the C&HRS-enabled SPS scheme.

where C is a constant depending on the properties of the sensing reconstruction matrix and k is the sparsity level of the signal.

- Select collided resources in order from L_3 for reuse distance evaluation.
- For each candidate collided resource R_k , the transmitting vehicle V_i identifies the interfering vehicle V_k , and computes its distance $d_{i,k}$ from the V_k . If $d_{i,k}$ exceeds the predefined reuse distance d_{reuse} , R_k is considered acceptable. Otherwise, the mechanism evaluates the next candidate resource R_{k+1} in L_3 . For the purposes of the study, d_{reuse} is set to 100 m in this work.
- Steps are repeated until $U_{min} - U$ resources are selected or L_3 is exhausted. If no suitable resources are found, the vehicle defers HRS to the next interval, leading to an HRS outage until the next interval.

3) Resource Congestion Control

To reduce the channel occupancy generated by V_i by occupying additional TF resources to perform HRS, a congestion control mechanism is adopted in which the V_i will not reserve the selected SPYDER resources for future transmissions rather it selects the SPYDER resources dynamically and drops some resources in SPYDER such that $|\Omega_s| \geq U_{min}$.

Finally, the performance of the allocated TF resources for both communication and radar sensing tasks is evaluated at the receiving vehicles. Each receiving vehicle generates an ISAC QoS report which is shared among neighboring vehicles. The exchange of QoS reports among vehicles helps in optimizing TF resource allocation.

IV. Radar Parameter Estimation

This section presents the proposed received signal processing framework to construct a high-resolution radar RD map, which is further used to estimate target parameters (i.e., range and relative velocity). First, the transmitted symbols are accounted for by performing an element-wise division of the received signal \mathbf{Y} by \mathbf{X} to yield the channel transfer function matrix $\mathbf{H} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_b \times M_b}$ as

$$\mathbf{H}_{n,m} \in \begin{cases} \frac{\mathbf{Y}_{n,m}}{\mathbf{X}_{n,m}}, & \text{if } \{n, m\} \in \Omega_{cs} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

where \mathbf{H} is a sparse matrix with non-zero entries located at the set of the indices $\Omega_{cs} \triangleq \Omega_c \cup \Omega_s$. Typically, a periodogram of \mathbf{H} is computed to construct the RD map as

$$\mathcal{P} = |\mathcal{F}_M \{ \mathcal{F}_N^{-1} \{ \mathbf{H} \} \}|^2, \quad (9)$$

which is a 2D-FFT over the channel transfer function \mathbf{H} . Applying the periodogram or 2D-FFT directly to the sparse channel matrix \mathbf{H} often results in degraded radar performance in terms of reduced SNR gain and random RD spurs/sidelobes. These RD independent sidelobes can create ghost target appearances, obscuring weaker targets, and ultimately increase the target misdetection rate. To overcome this, we adopt a CS algorithm namely Newtonized orthogonal matching pursuit (NOMP) that offers enhanced noise robustness and the ability to accurately estimate sensing parameters with sparse and unstructured OFDM grid, thereby improving target detection performance.

A. Two-Dimensional Newtonized Orthogonal Matching Pursuit (2D-NOMP)

The two dimensional Newtonized orthogonal matching pursuit (2D-NOMP) algorithm estimates the range and Doppler shift of targets in a continuous 2D parameter space, serving

as an off-grid sparse recovery method. The 2D-NOMP builds upon the conventional OMP algorithm, which iteratively identifies target parameters by selecting the column of the measurement matrix most correlated with the residual signal. However, the OMP algorithm suffers from a basis mismatch problem that is when a target's parameters do not align with the discrete grid points, the selected atom fails to accurately represent the target, leading to less accurate parameter estimation. To address this issue, we employ a low-complexity 2D-NOMP algorithm [25], which extends the OMP algorithm by incorporating Newton refinements to mitigate basis mismatch.

In (8), by removing the unused TF resources (i.e., zero entries), the matrix \mathbf{H} is compressed to \mathbf{H}_s . The compressed matrix \mathbf{H}_s is expressed in vector form as

$$\mathbf{h}_s = \sum_{p=1}^P \gamma_p \mathbf{a}^{\Omega_{cs}}(\tau_p, \alpha_p) + \tilde{\mathbf{z}}, \quad (10)$$

where $\mathbf{a}^{\Omega_{cs}}(\tau_p, \alpha_p) \in \mathbb{C}^{|\Omega_{cs}|}$ is the response vector corresponding to the p -th path. Specifically,

$$\mathbf{a}^{\Omega_{cs}}(\tau_p, \alpha_p) = [e^{-j2\pi n \Delta f \tau_p} e^{j2\pi m T_o \alpha_p}]_{\{n,m\} \in \Omega_{cs}}. \quad (11)$$

Thus, (10) can be rewritten as

$$\mathbf{h}_s = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{b} + \tilde{\mathbf{z}}, \quad (12)$$

where $\mathbf{A} = [\mathbf{a}^{\Omega_{cs}}(\tau_1, \alpha_1), \mathbf{a}^{\Omega_{cs}}(\tau_2, \alpha_2), \dots, \mathbf{a}^{\Omega_{cs}}(\tau_P, \alpha_P)] \in \mathbb{C}^{|\Omega_{cs}| \times P}$, $\mathbf{b} = [\gamma_1, \gamma_2, \dots, \gamma_P] \in \mathbb{C}^P$, and $\tilde{\mathbf{z}} \in \mathbb{C}^{|\Omega_{cs}|}$ represents the noise vector. The 2D-NOMP operates in the following three key steps.

- 1) **Grid-based Coarse Estimation:** The algorithm begins with a coarse estimation of target parameters by selecting the atom in the dictionary with the highest correlation to the residual signal. To reduce the computational complexity of this correlation step, we propose a low-complexity solution by exploiting the structure of the discrete sensing matrix $\bar{\mathbf{A}} = [\mathbf{a}(\bar{\tau}_1, \bar{\alpha}_1), \mathbf{a}(\bar{\tau}_2, \bar{\alpha}_1), \dots, \mathbf{a}(\bar{\tau}_{N_b}, \bar{\alpha}_{M_b})] \in \mathbb{C}^{|\Omega_{cs}| \times N_b M_b}$ using Fourier matrices as:

$$\bar{\mathbf{A}} = \mathbf{I}_s (\mathbf{F}_m^* \otimes \mathbf{F}_n), \quad (13)$$

where the matrix $\mathbf{I}_s \in \mathbb{B}^{|\Omega_{cs}| \times N_b M_b}$ serves as a binary selection matrix, while $\mathbf{F}_n \in \mathbb{C}^{N_b \times N_b}$ and $\mathbf{F}_m \in \mathbb{C}^{M_b \times M_b}$ are Fourier matrices. This decomposition enables leveraging the fast Fourier transform (FFT) for more efficient computation. To facilitate this, we define a matrix $\mathbf{R} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_b \times M_b}$, where the entries corresponding to the indices in Ω_{cs} are initialized with the values from the residual vector \mathbf{h}_r , i.e., $\mathbf{R}(\Omega_{cs}) = \mathbf{h}_r$.

The FFT is then used to compute the correlation as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{c}_p &= (\mathbf{I}_s (\mathbf{F}_m^* \otimes \mathbf{F}_n))^H \mathbf{h}_r \\ &= \text{vec} \left(\mathcal{F} (\mathcal{F}^{-1}(\mathbf{R}))^T \right) \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

Here, \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{F}^{-1} denote the FFT and IFFT operations, respectively, and $\text{vec}(\cdot)$ converts the resulting matrix

into a vector. The selected atoms are initial guesses for the target's parameters on the grid.

- 2) **Local Newton Refinements:** The on-grid estimates $(\hat{\tau}_p, \hat{\alpha}_p, \hat{\gamma}_p)$ are refined locally using Newton optimization to adjust the parameters off the grid, improving accuracy. The Newton refinement is done by

$$\begin{bmatrix} \hat{\tau}_p' \\ \hat{\alpha}_p' \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\tau}_p \\ \hat{\alpha}_p \end{bmatrix} - \ddot{\mathbf{S}}(\hat{\tau}_p, \hat{\alpha}_p, \hat{\gamma}_p)^{-1} \dot{\mathbf{S}}(\hat{\tau}_p, \hat{\alpha}_p, \hat{\gamma}_p), \quad (15)$$

where $\ddot{\mathbf{S}}$ and $\dot{\mathbf{S}}$ represent the Hessian matrix and Jacobian matrix, respectively. The entries of these matrices are derived in [25]. This refinement step minimizes the mismatch error between the true target's parameters and the discretized grid points by iterating over R_s times, where R_s represents the number of Newton refinements.

- 3) **Joint Newton Refinements:** After refining the parameters of newly identified targets, this step jointly optimizes all previously detected P targets' parameters as

$$\begin{bmatrix} \hat{\tau}_1'' \\ \hat{\alpha}_1'' \\ \vdots \\ \hat{\tau}_P'' \\ \hat{\alpha}_P'' \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\tau}_1' \\ \hat{\alpha}_1' \\ \vdots \\ \hat{\tau}_P' \\ \hat{\alpha}_P' \end{bmatrix} - \ddot{\mathbf{S}}(\mathcal{C}')^{-1} \dot{\mathbf{S}}(\mathcal{C}'), \quad (16)$$

where, $\mathcal{C}' = \{(\hat{\tau}_p', \hat{\alpha}_p', \hat{\gamma}_p') \mid p = 1, \dots, P\}$, $\ddot{\mathbf{S}}(\mathcal{C}') \in \mathbb{R}^{2P \times 2P}$ and $\dot{\mathbf{S}}(\mathcal{C}') \in \mathbb{R}^{2P \times 1}$ are block Hessian and block Jacobian matrices, which are given below.

$$\ddot{\mathbf{S}}(\mathcal{C}') = \begin{bmatrix} \ddot{\mathbf{S}}_{11} & \ddot{\mathbf{S}}_{12} & \cdots & \ddot{\mathbf{S}}_{1P} \\ \ddot{\mathbf{S}}_{21} & \ddot{\mathbf{S}}_{22} & \cdots & \ddot{\mathbf{S}}_{2P} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \ddot{\mathbf{S}}_{P1} & \ddot{\mathbf{S}}_{P2} & \cdots & \ddot{\mathbf{S}}_{PP} \end{bmatrix}, \dot{\mathbf{S}}(\mathcal{C}') = \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\mathbf{S}}_1 \\ \vdots \\ \dot{\mathbf{S}}_P \end{bmatrix}. \quad (17)$$

The expressions of the entries of the matrices $\ddot{\mathbf{S}}(\mathcal{C}')$, and $\dot{\mathbf{S}}(\mathcal{C}')$ are derived in [25]. This step ensures consistency and reduces the impact of any residual mismatch on the final estimates.

By integrating these steps, the 2D-NOMP effectively mitigates basis mismatch, achieving superior performance compared to standard OMP, particularly in scenarios where targets lie off the discretized grid points. The 2D-NOMP is summarized in Algorithm 1. The 2D-NOMP termination criterion is based on a CFAR-based threshold δ , which is selected based on the required probability of false alarm p_{fa} [34]. In Algorithm 1, we assume $\mathbf{a} = \mathbf{a}^{\Omega_{cs}}$ for clarity and brevity. The 2D-NOMP algorithm's details, including its Newton refinement steps for off-grid target detection, are thoroughly presented in [25]. Here, we summarize its key features and focus on its application to SPYDER grid-based radar sensing in the proposed RRA framework.

B. Computational Complexity

The Algorithm 1 has three main parts: Grid-based coarse estimation (steps 6-9), Local Newton refinements (steps 11-14), and Joint Newton refinement (steps 16-20), and the computational complexity of each part

Algorithm 1 2D-NOMP Algorithm [25]

```

1: Input:  $\mathbf{h}_s, \bar{\mathbf{A}}, \delta \triangleq \ln |\Omega_{cs}| - \ln(-\ln(1 - p_{fa}))$ 
2: Initial state:  $\mathbf{h}_r^0 = \mathbf{h}_s, \Pi_0 = \emptyset, p = 0, \mathbf{R}^0(\Omega_{cs}) = \mathbf{h}_r$ 
3: repeat
4:    $p = p + 1$ 
5:   Grid Based Estimation:
6:      $\mathbf{c}_p = \text{vec}(\mathcal{F}(\mathcal{F}^{-1}(\mathbf{R}^{p-1})))^T$ 
7:      $\Pi_p = \arg \max_j |\mathbf{c}_p(j)|^2$   $\triangleright$  Identify atom
8:      $(\hat{\tau}_p, \hat{\alpha}_p) = \text{ind2sub}(\text{size}(\mathbf{R}), \Pi_p)$   $\triangleright$  Grid estimate
9:      $\hat{\gamma}_p = \mathbf{a}^H(\hat{\tau}_p, \hat{\alpha}_p) \mathbf{h}_r^{p-1} / \|\mathbf{a}(\hat{\tau}_p, \hat{\alpha}_p)\|_2^2$   $\triangleright$  Gain
    update
10:    Local Newton Refinements:
11:      $(\hat{\tau}'_p, \hat{\alpha}'_p) = (\hat{\tau}_p, \hat{\alpha}_p) - \hat{\mathbf{S}}^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{S}} \triangleright$  Newton refinement
12:      $\hat{\gamma}'_p = \mathbf{a}^H(\hat{\tau}'_p, \hat{\alpha}'_p) \mathbf{h}_r^{p-1} / \|\mathbf{a}(\hat{\tau}'_p, \hat{\alpha}'_p)\|_2^2$ 
13:      $\mathbf{h}_r^p = \mathbf{h}_r^{p-1} - \hat{\gamma}'_p \mathbf{a}(\hat{\tau}'_p, \hat{\alpha}'_p)$   $\triangleright$  Residual update
14:      $\mathcal{C}' = \mathcal{C}' \cup (\hat{\tau}'_p, \hat{\alpha}'_p, \hat{\gamma}'_p)$   $\triangleright$  Local refined estimates
15:    Joint Newton Refinements:
16:      $(\hat{\tau}''_p, \hat{\alpha}''_p) = (\hat{\tau}'_p, \hat{\alpha}'_p) - \hat{\mathbf{S}}(\mathcal{C}')^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{S}}(\mathcal{C}') \triangleright 1 \leq p \leq K$ 
17:      $\mathbf{b}_{\mathcal{C}''} = \mathbf{A}_{\mathcal{C}''}^\dagger \mathbf{h}_s$   $\triangleright$  Least squares gain update
18:      $\mathbf{h}_r^p = \mathbf{h}_s - \mathbf{A}_{\mathcal{C}''} \mathbf{b}_{\mathcal{C}''}$   $\triangleright$  Residual update
19:      $\mathbf{R}^p(\Omega_s) = \mathbf{h}_r^p$   $\triangleright$   $\mathbf{R}$  matrix update
20:      $\Pi_p = \Pi_{p-1} \cup \text{sub2ind}(\text{size}(\mathbf{R}), \hat{\tau}''_p, \hat{\alpha}''_p)$ 
21: until  $\max |\mathbf{c}_p|^2 \leq \delta$   $\triangleright$  stopping criterion
22: Output:  $\mathbf{b}_{\mathcal{C}''}, \Pi$ 

```

is $\mathcal{O}(N_b M_b (\log(N_b) + \log(M_b)))$, $\mathcal{O}(p R_s |\Omega_{cs}|)$, and $\mathcal{O}(|\Omega_{cs}| p^2 + p^3)$, respectively, where p represents the current number of iterations. We compare 2D-NOMP's computational complexity with that of Atomic Norm Minimization (ANM). ANM is a state-of-the-art gridless super-resolution method that formulates the parameter estimation problem as a semi-definite programming (SDP) problem. The computational complexity of ANM is at least $\mathcal{O}((N_b M_b)^{3.5})$. This complexity grows rapidly with the data size, making ANM computationally prohibitive for large-scale vehicular ISAC scenarios, where high-dimensional data is frequently encountered. In contrast, the proposed 2D-NOMP algorithm significantly reduces computational complexity by leveraging FFT operations and Newtonized iterative refinements. Specifically, in the grid-based coarse estimation step, 2D-NOMP replaces the conventional correlation operation (i.e., matrix-vector multiplications with the sensing matrix) used in the vanilla OMP with an efficient two dimensional fast Fourier transform (2D-FFT) operation, reducing the complexity to $\mathcal{O}(N_b M_b (\log N_b + \log M_b))$. Furthermore, in the joint Newton refinement step, 2D-NOMP performs iterative Newton refinements with a complexity of $\mathcal{O}(|\Omega_{cs}| p^2 + p^3)$. This step allows 2D-NOMP to achieve off-grid parameter estimation without requiring large-scale convex optimization. While ANM achieves superior estimation accuracy, its high computational burden makes it impractical for real-time vehicular ISAC setups. On the other hand, 2D-NOMP offers a favorable trade-off between complexity and estimation per-

formance. Despite being slightly less accurate than ANM, it achieves near-optimal range-Doppler estimation with orders of magnitude lower complexity, making it highly suitable for real-time vehicular ISAC applications where computational efficiency is a critical requirement.

V. Simulation Results

In this section, we describe the simulation setup and performance analysis to evaluate the performance of our proposed RRA approach.

A. Simulation Scenario

To evaluate the performance of the proposed RRA framework, a two-way highway scenario is simulated that comprises a variable number of vehicles randomly distributed along a 2 km long road with a width of 24 m (4 m for each lane). The traffic traces are generated using the Simulation of Urban Mobility (SUMO) tool [35], which provides realistic mobility patterns and vehicle dynamics. These traces are fed into our proposed RRA framework, implemented in MATLAB. Inspired by the WiLabV2XSim simulator [36], our simulation framework is designed to assess the performance of the proposed RRA scheme. The main simulation settings and parameters are shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1. Simulation Parameters

Category	Parameter	Value
Scenario (Highway)	Number of lanes	3 in each direction (6 in total)
	Lane size	2 km \times 4 m
	Vehicle Density	[25 50 75 100] veh/km
	Vehicle Speed	$\mathcal{N}(90, 10)$ km/h
	Max. sensing range	500 m
PHY	Carrier frequency	5.9 GHz
	PC5 Bandwidth	10 MHz
	SCS (Δf)	30 kHz
	Antenna gain	3 dBi
	Maximum Tx power	23 dBm
	Noise figure	9 dB
	Channel model	ISAC-enabled V2V [37]
ISAC-enabled SPS	Packet size	350 bytes (CAMs)
	Packet Tx frequency	10 Hz
	MCS	11
	T_{sense}	1000 ms
	T_1, T_2	1 ms, 100 ms, respectively
	p_{keep}	0.4
	RRI	100 ms
	SL-RSRP Threshold	-126 dBm
	B_s	50 MHz ($\Delta r = 6$ m)
	T_s	10 ms ($\Delta v = 2.5$ m/s)

B. Performance Evaluation

We evaluate the performance of the proposed framework in terms of radar sensing and communication performance.

1) Radar Performance Evaluation

In this section, a numerical analysis of the radar performance under the proposed RRA framework is performed. First, we analyze and compare the radar sensing performance in terms of range profiles and velocity profiles using different resource grid structures and processing algorithms. The results provide insight into the impact of grid sparsity on radar detection and resolution performance. Figure 8 illustrates the range profiles obtained using the FFT processing and the Newtonized orthogonal matching pursuit (NOMP) on radar signals across three resource grid configurations: the Full grid with no TF interleaving, the Equispaced grid with uniform TF interleaving, and the SPYDER grid. To address the potential SNR degradation caused by sparsity in the Equispaced and SPYDER grids, the power of their REs is boosted uniformly. Among the profiles, the SPYDER grid processed with the NOMP algorithm demonstrates exceptional performance, achieving more than 50 dB suppression of range sidelobes compared to the SPYDER grid processed with the FFT. This improvement underscores the effectiveness of the NOMP in reconstructing sparse signals. In contrast, the Equispaced grid processed with the FFT shows equipower aliasing peaks in the range profile due to its periodic subcarrier selection (every 24-th subcarrier). These aliasing artifacts compromise the clarity of the range spectrum, highlighting the limitations of uniform interleaving under standard FFT processing. Similarly, Figure 9 presents

FIGURE 8. Range profile comparison of different resource grids.

the velocity profiles for the same resource grid configurations and processing algorithms. Similar trends are observed in the comparison of velocity profiles. The SPYDER grid processed with the NOMP algorithm outperforms other resource grids, achieving more than 65 dB velocity sidelobes reduction compared to FFT processing of the SPYDER grid. However, FFT processing of the Equispaced grid, where every 14-th OFDM symbol is selected, introduces aliasing artifacts.

FIGURE 9. Velocity profile comparison of different resource grids.

Figure 10 illustrates the variation of the PSLR in range and velocity as a function of the percentage of TF resources occupied by the SPYDER grid. The PSLR is defined as the ratio of the peak power of the main lobe to the peak power of the strongest sidelobe in the range or Doppler profile. In this analysis, a scene with a single target is simulated without any windowing function, and the number of TF resources is varied from 0.1% to 10% to observe its impact on PSLR. As the percentage of TF resources increases, the sparsity level of the channel decreases. This reduction in sparsity results in a consistent improvement in PSLR for both the FFT and NOMP based processing. The NOMP based processing outperforms the FFT by achieving significant PSLR gains. Specifically, the range PSLR improves by up to 40 dB, and the velocity PSLR improves by up to 60 dB when NOMP processing is applied.

FIGURE 10. Range and velocity PSLR for increasing resource occupancy in the SPYDER grid. PSLR in the range cut (top); PSLR in the velocity cut (bottom).

FIGURE 11. Overview of sensing scenario and RD maps. (a) One-way highway traffic scenario. (b) 2D-FFT based RD map for low resolution sensing (LRS) with communication resource block. (c) 2D-NOMP based RD map for high resolution sensing (HRS) with the SPYDER grid.

Next, we evaluate the radar sensing performance in a vehicular scenario depicted in Figure 11a by generating two RD maps: One RD map for LRS shown in Figure 11b and the second RD map for HRS shown in Figure 11c. The scenario consists of a transmitting vehicle (Tx), a receiving vehicle (Rx), three target vehicles (Tar1, Tar2, Tar3), and a cluster of scatterers (Cluster). The radius of the dashed circle around the Tx and Rx represents the sensing range of 200 m. The positions and velocities of the Tx, Rx, Tar1, Tar2, Tar3, and the Cluster center are defined in Table 2. The RD map for LRS

TABLE 2. Scenario Parameters

Component	Position (m)	Velocity (m/s)	RCS (dBsm)
Tx	(200, 10, 1.5)	(20, 0, 0)	-
Rx	(300, 10, 1.5)	(10, 0, 0)	-
Tar1	(125, 20, 0)	(5, 0, 0)	10
Tar2	(350, 20, 0)	(5, 0, 0)	10
Tar3	(250, 25, 0)	(5, 0, 0)	10
Cluster	(250, -10, 0)	(0, 0, 0)	-15

is obtained by applying the 2D-FFT on the channel transfer function matrix corresponding to contiguous TF resources allocated for data packet transmission. The data packet, sized 350 bytes, occupies 2 subchannels in the frequency domain, with each subchannel containing 10 PRBs (240 subcarriers) corresponding to a bandwidth of 7.2 MHz and a range resolution of 41.6 m. In the time domain, the packet spans one slot (14 OFDM symbols equivalent to 0.5 ms), resulting in a velocity resolution of 50.8 m s^{-1} . Using this resource grid, the RD map is generated via the 2D-FFT followed by a cell-averaging constant false alarm rate (CA-CFAR) detector configured with false alarm probability of 1×10^{-6} . To refine the results, off-grid range-Doppler estimates are obtained through linear interpolation of the on-grid estimates. Despite these efforts, the LRS RD map detects only the Tx peak, dominated by the strong LOS component, while it fails to detect the peaks of the targets (Tar1, Tar2, and Tar3) as shown in Figure 11b. Moreover, the difference between the bistatic distance of Tar3 and the distance of Tx to Rx is

4.4 m which is less than the range resolution, Tar3 and Tx peaks are indistinguishable in the LRS RD map, emphasizing the need for high-precision sensing. On the other hand, the HRS employs the SPYDER grid, configured with a bandwidth of 50 MHz and a time duration of 10 ms. This setup significantly improves the sensing resolution, providing a range resolution of 6 m and a velocity resolution of 2.5 m/s. The HRS RD map is generated using the 2D-NOMP algorithm, which outperforms the 2D-FFT approach by accurately detecting and distinguishing all target peaks from the Tx peak. For example, the closely spaced Tar3 and Tx peaks are distinctly identified due to the joint Newton optimization step in the 2D-NOMP algorithm. Moreover, weaker targets such as Tar1 and Tar2, which remain undetected in the LRS RD map, are visible and accurately identified in the HRS RD map. However, a spurious peak representing a ghost target, is also detected by the 2D-NOMP algorithm, and can be mitigated by adjusting the CFAR-based threshold or increasing the Newton refinement steps in the algorithm. This comparison demonstrates the super-resolution capability of the 2D-NOMP algorithm, making it highly effective for high-resolution radar sensing applications.

Next to analyze the impact of synchronization errors i.e., TO and CFO on the sensing performance, we produce the results in Figure 12 and Figure 13 in the form of distance and velocity profiles, and RD maps respectively. Figure 12 illustrates the impact of TO and CFO on range and velocity estimation in vehicular bistatic ISAC scenario shown in Figure 11a. For the sake of simplicity, the scenario considers a single target, where the Tx is treated as a virtual target. The range profiles are plotted for different TO values (0, 10, 100, and 500 ns) and a fixed CFO value of 100 Hz. TO introduces a shift in the estimated range of the target. As TO increases, the deviation from the true range also increases. For instance, a TO of 10 ns results in a range estimation error of approximately 2.5 m, while TO values of 50 ns and 100 ns lead to errors of about 6 m and 15 m, respectively. On the other hand, the velocity profiles are plotted for different CFO values (0, 100, 500, and 1000 Hz)

and a fixed TO value of 10 ns. CFO leads to a shift in the estimated velocity profile. A higher CFO results in a greater deviation from the true velocity. For example, a CFO of 100 Hz introduces a velocity estimation error of more than 12.5 m/s, while CFO values of 500 Hz and 1000 Hz lead to errors of approximately 23 m/s and 35 m/s, respectively. This range and velocity shift is detrimental in high-precision sensing applications where accurate target localization is required.

FIGURE 12. Impact of TO and CFO on range and velocity estimation: (top) Increasing TO by keeping CFO fixed shifts the target’s peak in the range profile, (bottom) while increasing CFO by keeping TO fixed causes a deviation in the velocity profile.

Figure 13 presents two RD maps of the scenario shown in Figure 11a, illustrating the combined effect of TO and CFO on range and velocity estimation. The first RD map, shown in Figure 13a, corresponds to $TO = 10$ ns and $CFO = 100$ Hz, while the second RD map, shown in Figure 13b, corresponds to $TO = 50$ ns and $CFO = 500$ Hz. In first RD map, the estimation errors in both range and velocity are relatively small due to the minor TO and CFO values. The target peaks remain close to their true positions with distance error less than 3 m and velocity error less than 2.5 m/s. As TO and CFO increase, the errors in range and velocity estimation become more pronounced as shown in Figure 13b. The RD peaks shift along both axes, reducing the accuracy of target localization. Additionally, there is a minor reduction in SNR, but it remains negligible since the TO is within the cyclic prefix (CP) duration, preventing inter-symbol interference (ISI), and the CFO is significantly smaller than the SCS, minimizing inter-carrier interference (ICI). Overall, TO and CFO introduce systematic errors that shift the RD map along both axes, reducing the accuracy of target estimation and limiting the maximum unambiguous range and velocity measurements in bistatic ISAC systems. Proper synchronization techniques are essential to mitigate these effects and ensure reliable sensing performance.

(a) RD map with $TO = 10$ ns and $CFO = 100$ Hz

(b) RD map with $TO = 50$ ns and $CFO = 500$ Hz

FIGURE 13. RD maps illustrating the combined effect of TO and CFO on target estimation. (a) The RD map corresponds to $TO = 10$ ns and $CFO = 100$ Hz, showing minor estimation errors. (b) The RD map with $TO = 50$ ns and $CFO = 500$ Hz exhibits larger estimation error in both range and velocity due to increased synchronization errors.

Figure 14 compares the performance of the two dimensional orthogonal matching pursuit (2D-OMP) and 2D-NOMP algorithms in detecting radar targets under both on-grid and off-grid conditions. A scenario with five point targets — Tar1, Tar2, Tar3, Tar4, and Tar5 — is simulated, with their respective true ranges and velocities set to (9.62 m, 10.17 m/s), (25 m, -25 m/s), (50 m, 20 m/s), (80.13 m, -15.25 m/s), and (100 m, 30 m/s) respectively. All targets have the same RCS of 10 dBsm. Among these targets, Tar1 and Tar4 are placed on the grid points, while the others lie off-grid. The results indicate that the 2D-OMP algorithm can detect all five targets. However, for off-grid targets e.g., Tar2 and Tar3, the 2D-OMP suffers from the basis mismatch problem, leading to inaccurate estimations. Instead of identifying the true parameters (range and velocity) of Tar2 and Tar3, the 2D-OMP associates nearby grid points with spurious target detections. In contrast, the 2D-NOMP algorithm demonstrates superior performance by

accurately estimating the parameters of both on-grid and off-grid targets. This improvement is attributed to the ability of 2D-NOMP to overcome the basis mismatch problem through its off-grid refinement capabilities.

FIGURE 14. Off-grid target estimation comparison between 2D-OMP algorithm and 2D-NOMP algorithm.

We evaluate the estimation accuracies of 2D-FFT, 2D-OMP, and 2D-NOMP in terms of RMSE as a function of SNR as shown in Figure 15. The RMSE in range and velocity estimation is evaluated for a single target case by running 500 independent Monte Carlo (MC) simulations for each SNR. In each MC iteration, the subset Ω_s of resources is randomly selected to form the SPYDER grid, and the noise matrix \mathbf{Z} is also randomly generated, following a Gaussian distribution. The target's range and velocity are randomly chosen from $\mathcal{U}(50 \text{ m}, 1500 \text{ m})$ and $\mathcal{U}(-30 \text{ m/s}, 30 \text{ m/s})$, respectively. The CRB provided in [38] is taken as the benchmark. The CRBs for range and velocity estimation are expressed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{range}^2 &\geq \frac{3c^2}{\text{SNR}8\pi^2 M_b N_b (n^2 - 1) \Delta f^2}, \\ \sigma_{velocity}^2 &\geq \frac{3c^2}{\text{SNR}8\pi^2 f_c^2 M_b N_b (m^2 - 1) T_o^2}. \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

The RMSE results demonstrate that the 2D-NOMP algorithm not only outperforms the other approaches but also gradually approaches the CRB¹. On the other hand, since 2D-FFT and OMP support only on-grid target searches, their RMSEs in both range and velocity estimation do not improve with increasing SNR.

2) Communication Performance Evaluation

In this section, V2V communication performance is evaluated in terms of various performance metrics such as PRR,

¹Here $R_s = 10$ Newton refinements are assumed in the 2D-NOMP algorithm.

FIGURE 15. RMSE of range (top) and velocity (bottom) estimation comparison of 2D-FFT, 2D-OMP and 2D-NOMP algorithms.

CBR, and PID. The PRR is a critical metric for evaluating the V2V communication reliability. The PRR is defined as the proportion of successfully received packets at the Rx vehicles within an awareness range (e.g., 300 m) of a Tx vehicle. Mathematically, the PRR is written as:

$$\text{PRR} = \frac{1}{P_t} \sum_{j=1}^{P_t} \frac{N_{\text{success},j}}{N_{\text{Rx},j}}, \quad (19)$$

where P_t represents the total number of packets sent by the Tx vehicle, $N_{\text{success},j}$ is the number of vehicles with successful reception for the j -th packet, and $N_{\text{Rx},j}$ is the number of Rx vehicles located in the awareness range of the Tx vehicle for the j -th packet. In V2V communication, the successful reception of a data packet depends on its SINR at the Rx vehicle compared to a predefined SINR threshold (SINR_{th}). A packet is deemed successfully received if its SINR exceeds SINR_{th} , otherwise, the reception is considered a failure. The SINR threshold is calculated below as given in [36]:

$$\text{SINR}_{\text{th}} = 2^{\frac{N_{sc} M_{sym} Q_m CR}{T_{slot} B \phi}} - 1, \quad (20)$$

where N_{sc} and M_{sym} denote the number of subcarriers and OFDM symbols in a PRB, respectively, Q_m is the modulation order, CR is the effective coding rate, T_{slot} is the duration of one slot, B represents the bandwidth of a PRB, and ϕ is the loss factor, set to 0.4 as recommended in [39]. Figure 16 shows the PRR performance evaluated for three configurations: 1) C&LRS-enabled SPS which employs the conventional SPS scheme for communication and LRS and serves as the benchmark, 2) C&HRS-enabled SPS with full grid and 3) C&HRS-enabled SPS with SPYDER grid which adopts the SPYDER grid to fulfill HRS requirements. The PRR is simulated as a function of the Tx-Rx distance, considering a vehicle density of 50 veh/km and evaluating performance up to Tx-Rx distance of 300 m with a step size of 10 m. The V2X communication reliability requirement

is set at a PRR threshold of 95%. The results show that the PRR for the C&LRS-enabled SPS configuration remains above 95% up to Tx-Rx distance of approximately 180 m, demonstrating its robust performance in meeting the V2X reliability requirements. For C&HRS-enabled SPS with the full grid, the PRR starts above 95% but degrades rapidly with increasing Tx-Rx distance, dropping significantly after 60 m. This performance degradation is primarily due to the higher resource demands of the full grid, which result in increased interference and reduced SINR. In contrast, the C&HRS-enabled SPS with the SPYDER grid demonstrates a 14.2% PRR improvement over the full grid. The SPYDER grid maintains a PRR comparable to the benchmark configuration, staying above 95% up to a distance of 180 m and performing consistently across the 300 m range. This improvement highlights the SPYDER grid's ability to efficiently balance the resource requirements of HRS with the reliability demands of V2V communication.

FIGURE 16. PRR performance comparison of the standard SPS and the proposed approach.

Figure 17 presents the PRR comparison of C&HRS-enabled SPS with the full grid and C&HRS-enabled SPS with the SPYDER grid under varying vehicle densities: 25 veh/km, 50 veh/km, 75 veh/km, and 100 veh/km. Both approaches exhibit a similar trend of decreasing PRR with increasing vehicle density but at different decreasing rates. The observed decrease in PRR with higher vehicle density can be attributed to increased resource collisions due to the random resource selection mechanism. As the vehicle density increases, the likelihood of multiple vehicles selecting the same resources also increases, leading to packet collisions and subsequent degradation in the PRR. This phenomenon underscores the importance of efficient resource allocation mechanisms to mitigate interference and enhance communication reliability. The C&HRS-enabled SPS with the SPYDER grid demonstrates superior performance compared to the full grid, particularly in terms of the enhanced reliability distance (ERD). The ERD represents the additional

distance at which the PRR remains greater than or equal to 95% in the SPYDER grid configuration as compared to the full grid configuration under the same vehicle density. The results show that the SPYDER grid consistently achieves better PRR performance across all vehicle densities. For example, at vehicle densities of 25 veh/km, 50 veh/km, 75 veh/km, and 100 veh/km, the SPYDER grid achieves an ERD of 75 m, 105 m, 115 m, and 117 m, respectively compared to the full grid. Notably for 25 veh/km with the SPYDER grid, the PRR curve exhibits an abrupt turn around at 200 m. This discontinuity is attributed primarily to the low vehicle density, where the limited number of vehicles within the awareness range leads to increased statistical fluctuations in PRR measurements. Overall the PRR results highlight the ability of the C&HRS-enabled SPS with SPYDER grid to efficiently balance resource allocation, reducing the impact of resource collisions and maintaining high communication reliability even in dense vehicular networks.

FIGURE 17. PRR performance comparison of the proposed approach with full and SPYDER grids under varying vehicle densities.

Figure 18 presents a comparison of the probability of resource collision (PRC) between C&HRS-enabled SPS with the full grid and the SPYDER grid as a function of vehicle density. The PRC is defined as the ratio of the number of resources selected by two or more vehicles to the total number of allocated resources. In the case of the full grid, the PRC exhibits very high values even at lower vehicle densities. For the SPYDER grid, the PRC depends on the number of TF resources occupied by the grid. We call it SPYDER resource occupancy (RO). A higher RO results in a higher PRC value. The PRC values of the SPYDER grid are significantly lower than those of the full grid across all vehicle densities and different ROs of 0.1%, 1%, 5%, and 10%. The dependency of PRC on the RO in the SPYDER grid provides a flexible mechanism to balance collision probability and resource utilization efficiency.

Figure 19 shows the CBR comparison among aforementioned approaches. The CBR is defined as the ratio

FIGURE 18. Impact of SPYDER grid’s resource occupancy on the PRC under varying vehicle densities.

of resources experiencing a power level higher than a specified threshold to the total number of resources in the previous 100 subframes. It indicates the congestion level of radio resources. The simulation results are presented as box plots under different vehicle densities: 25 veh/km, 50 veh/km, 75 veh/km, and 100 veh/km. As expected, the CBR increases with an increase in vehicle density. This is due to the higher competition for radio resources at higher vehicle densities, leading to a higher proportion of resources exceeding the power threshold. The trend of increasing CBR is most prominent in the C&HRS-enabled SPS with full grid, indicating a higher level of resource congestion. In contrast, the CBR values for C&LRS-enabled SPS and C&HRS-enabled SPS with the SPYDER grid are almost similar, suggesting that with the SPYDER grid, the resource congestion is managed more effectively than the full grid configuration. This is because the SPYDER grid occupies minimum TF resources that are not reserved like communication resources and they are selected dynamically at the time of HRS.

Figure 20 shows the PID comparison for the aforementioned approaches. The PID is defined as the time elapsed between two successive successful receptions of different packets transmitted from the Tx vehicle to the Rx vehicle. The performance is evaluated in terms of the complementary cumulative distribution function (CCDF) of PID under two vehicle densities: 50 veh/km and 100 veh/km. At 50 veh/km, the resource demand is low, resulting in minimal resource contention and interference. Both the full grid and SPYDER grid configurations perform similarly, as the sparse and dynamic nature of the SPYDER grid has little impact when resources are abundant. However, at 100 veh/km, resource scarcity and contention increase. The full grid approach suffers from higher overhead due to coordinated resource management, while the SPYDER grid leverages its uncoordinated and sparse resource selection mechanism,

FIGURE 19. Resource Congestion comparison of the standard SPS and the proposed approach with full and SPYDER grids.

which reduces collision probability and efficiently manages interference through its resource reuse distance judgment. By dynamically spreading radar resources across the time-frequency domain, the SPYDER grid minimizes resource contention and interference, aligning its PID performance closely with the benchmark C&LRS-enabled SPS. This highlights that while the SPYDER grid matches the full grid’s PID performance at low density, it excels at higher densities by maintaining robust performance through dynamic resource utilization.

FIGURE 20. PID performance comparisons under vehicle densities of 50 veh/km (top), and 100 veh/km (bottom).

VI. Conclusion and Future Work

In this paper, we presented an in-depth analysis of the proposed radio resource allocation (RRA) framework for Integrated Sensing and Communication (ISAC) in a multiuser sidelink setup. The proposed scheme introduces a sparse and dynamically interleaved time-frequency (TF) resource grid,

known as SPYDER, to enable high resolution sensing (HRS) with minimal resource occupancy. By eliminating inter-vehicle coordination, the SPYDER grid reduces signaling overhead and ensures robust sensing and communication performance in high-mobility, dense vehicular environments. A compressed sensing framework employing the NOMP algorithm was adopted to avoid degradation in the radar performance introduced by the SPYDER grid. The comprehensive simulations reveal that the proposed RRA scheme significantly enhances radar sensing and communication performance in the multiuser sidelink ISAC system. The performance of the C&HRS-enabled SPS with the SPYDER grid remains comparable to that of the standard SPS scheme, outperforming the full grid approach in terms of packet reception ratio (PRR), channel busy ratio (CBR), and packet inter-reception Delay (PID). These findings highlight the efficacy of the SPYDER grid-based RRA scheme in addressing the key challenges of ISAC in spectrum-scarce and dynamic vehicular networks. Despite these advancements, synchronization errors—particularly time offset (TO) and carrier frequency offset (CFO)—can still degrade sensing performance by shifting range-Doppler (RD) estimations. Future research will therefore explore advanced synchronization techniques specifically tailored for ISAC-enabled networks, including robust TO and CFO estimation methods that preserve sensing parameters. Additionally, integrating machine learning approaches for dynamic resource allocation and interference mitigation could further enhance the adaptability of the proposed scheme in dense vehicular environments. Furthermore, experimental validation using real-world vehicular testbeds would provide critical insights into the practical feasibility and limitations of the proposed RRA framework. We hope that the insights presented in this paper will contribute to future standardization efforts in the ongoing evolution of C-V2X technology.

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